

Relaxing the Goldschmidt tolerance factor: sizable incorporation of the guanidinium cation into a two-dimensional Ruddlesden- Popper perovskite

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Abstract

The two-dimensional (2D) hybrid perovskites, in particular the Ruddlesden-Popper (RP) phase, exhibit excellent optoelectronic properties, higher flexibility in the employed large organic cations and an enhanced stability against the environmental agents compared to the three-dimensional (3D) perovskites. However, the small organic cations inserted into the octahedral voids have been limited so far to those three fulfilling the Goldschmidt tolerance factor (t) despite the relaxed structure of the 2D RP perovskites. In this work, the incorporation of the large guanidinium (Gua) cation into the octahedral sites of the “perovskite slabs” has been explored for the first time in 2D RP perovskites. Thus, the methylammonium (MA) cation in the $\text{PEA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite (PEA = phenylethylammonium) has been gradually substituted by the Gua cation to synthesize thin films of the mixed cation $\text{PEA}_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{Gua}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite. X-ray Diffraction (XRD) and Grazing-Incidence Wide-Angle X-ray Scattering (GIWAXS) measurements have revealed a regular expansion of the unit cell when increasing the Gua content up to 90% proving the sequential insertion into the lattice of the Gua having a larger ionic radius than that of the MA cation. Furthermore, the preferential orientation of the $\text{PEA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite films with the ($hk0$) planes parallel to the substrate is maintained up to a limit value of 60% Gua content. Importantly, the combined analysis of the steady-state and time-resolved absorption and photoluminescence (PL) spectra have revealed a change in the distribution of the n -members of the 2D RP perovskites towards phases with lower n values upon increasing the Gua content. The position and intensity of the photoluminescence is modulated within the $\text{PEA}_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{Gua}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite, allowing to fine tune the PL to each of the low dimensional perovskites ($n = 2, 3, 4$ and 5) at high Gua content ($\geq 70\%$). We have fabricated solar cells based on the mixed cation $\text{PEA}_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{Gua}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskites with PCE values similar to those of the reference cell ($\sim 2.5\%$) up to percentages of Gua of 20%. The unencapsulated devices have shown a significant enhancement of the stability after 750 hours demonstrating the positive effect of the Gua cation on the degradation of the 2D RP perovskites.

Introduction

Three-dimensional (3D) hybrid halide perovskites have emerged as a breakthrough in the field of photovoltaic and optoelectronic devices although their low stability against the environmental agents as heat, humidity and oxygen needs to be addressed if commercial devices are considered to be placed on the market.¹⁻⁶ Two-dimensional (2D) layered hybrid perovskites are becoming an alternative to the 3D counterparts due to its enhanced stability and also due to their structural versatility allowing the fine control of the optoelectronic properties of these compounds.⁷⁻¹² The 2D layered perovskites are theoretically obtained by slicing the 3D parent materials along a specific crystallographic plane, generating “perovskite slabs” which can be connected to each other by a wide variety of organic cations since the size limitation is more flexible compared to that in the 3D counterparts. These organic cations are responsible for the structural integrity of the 2D layered perovskites through the electrostatic attraction between the negative charge of the halide anions in the octahedra and the positive charges of the ammonium cations. However, despite the enhanced stability of the 2D layered perovskites, additional modifications of the lattice structure are necessary to avoid the final degradation of these 2D materials.

The 2D layered perovskites can be classified according to the cutting crystallographic plane resulting in (100)-, (110)-, and (111)-oriented layered perovskites.¹³ The (100)-oriented perovskites are by far the most studied structures which can be categorized as the Ruddlesden-Popper (RP) phase, the Dion-Jacobson (DJ) phase and the Aurivillius (AV) phase with the following general formulas $A'A_{n-1}B_nX_{3n+1}$, $A'A_{n-1}B_nX_{3n+1}$ and $(Bi_2X_2)A_{n-1}B_nX_{3n+1}$, respectively, where A , A' and B are cations and X is a halogen.¹³ The Ruddlesden-Popper phase is the most common 2D layered perovskite implemented in optoelectronic devices showing excellent performances. However, the principal feature that governs the optoelectronic properties of the 2D layered perovskites is the thickness of the “perovskite slabs” which ranges from one layer of octahedra ($n = 1$) to infinitive layers ($n = \infty$). Thus, the 2D layered perovskites with low dimensionality ($n < 5$) exhibit high stability and strong exciton confinement while the 2D perovskites with high n values present strong degradation against the environmental factors and low exciton binding

energies.^{14,15} The nature of the large organic cations (A') employed in the 2D RP perovskites plays a fundamental role to define the structural properties of the material. Despite the wide variety of molecules that can be incorporated as A' cations, the majority of the articles reporting optoelectronic applications for the Ruddlesden-Popper phase utilizes phenylethylammonium (PEA) and butylammonium (BA) and in less extent penthylammonium (PA) and benzylammonium (BzA). Regarding the A cation, methylammonium (MA) is the archetypal small cation localized in the octahedral voids of the “perovskite slabs”. The Goldschmidt tolerance factor (t) applicable to the 3D hybrid perovskites predicts that formamidinium (FA) or cesium can also be incorporated into the octahedral sites forming a single A -cation 3D perovskite, however, in the 2D perovskites, only the $n = 2$ members have been reported to accommodate single FA, Cs or guanidinium (Gua) perovskites.^{16–18} Following the A -site cation engineering approach of the 3D perovskites, recent studies have reported the incorporation of FA or Cs together with MA in 2D RP perovskites to fabricate solar devices with enhanced performance compared to those with only the MA cation.^{19–21} Other cations that do not fulfil the tolerance factor as rubidium ($t < 0.8$), ethylammonium or guanidinium ($t > 1.0$) have been demonstrated to partially incorporate into the lattice of the 3D counterparts, but not yet in the 2D layered perovskites.^{22–25} Thus, the inclusion of cations that neglect the tolerance factor in the “perovskite slabs” of the 2D RP perovskites may expand the structural diversity of these materials opening the way to new optoelectronic properties or enhanced thermodynamic stability.

In this work, we focus on the fabrication of spin-coated films of 2D RP perovskites with phenylethylammonium ($\text{PEA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$) where the small organic cation MA is sequentially substituted by the large guanidinium (Gua) cation forming the mixed A -cation $\text{PEA}_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{Gua}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite. We have investigated the influence of the Gua cation on the structure and orientation of the 2D perovskite films and on the optoelectronic properties of the material. Remarkably, large percentages of Gua (up to 90%) can be incorporated into the 2D RP structure in opposition to the case of the 3D perovskites (limit of 25%). In all 2D RP perovskites, due to thermodynamic mixing during the film casting, a wide distribution of RP phases with n values from 1 to ∞ are formed. In our mixed A -cation $\text{PEA}_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{Gua}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskites, the addition of Gua entails a

significant modification of this distribution causing a depletion of the RP phases with higher n values and a simultaneous rise of the content of low dimensional phases ($n < 5$). The addition of Gua to the 2D RP perovskite allows to control the intensity and position of the photoluminescence due to the modulation in the distribution of n -members. The thermal and environmental stability of these mixed A-cation 2D RP perovskites have been investigated in solar devices resulting in an enhanced performance with respect to the reference $\text{PEA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite.

Results

The 2D RP perovskite with formula $\text{PEA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ ($n = 3$) has the honor of being the first layered hybrid perovskite implemented in a solar device in 2014.⁷ From the early times, it was clear that the three main experimental parameters controlling the quality of the films were the hot-casting (HC) temperature, the solvent and the concentration used in the precursor solution.^{26,27} We have initially investigated the influence of these three parameters in the structure of the $\text{PEA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite by using X-ray diffraction (XRD) and steady-state absorption spectroscopy. We are interested in finding the optimal experimental conditions to prepare films of low dimensional 2D RP perovskites with high crystallinity and preferential orientation which are the two required characteristics for high-performance optoelectronic devices.

Figure S2 shows the absorption spectra (A) and XRD patterns (B) of films of $\text{PEA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ prepared from a 1.2 M solution in dimethylformamide (DMF) at different HC temperatures, from 25 °C to 120 °C. The intensity of the absorption signals and reflection peaks grows upon increasing the HC temperature from 25 °C to 90 °C, revealing a higher thickness and likely a better crystallization of the films. At 100 °C HC temperature, we observe a broadening, decrease and shift of the Bragg reflections which are converted into narrow and intense signals at 120 °C HC temperature. The position of these reflection peaks at 14.09° and 28.44° together with the clear enlargement of the absorption onset around 780 nm indicate the preferred formation of the 3D MAPbI_3 at this high HC temperature. In addition, we have performed Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) of the 2D RP perovskite films at different HC temperature to assess the morphology of the surface. The SEM image at low HC temperature (25 °C) shown in Figure S3

displays pinholes while the film exposed to 120 °C presents a coarse-grained surface. Both morphological features are not appropriate for fabricating optimum optoelectronic devices. HC temperatures of 55 °C and 100 °C produce films including small particles that are usually assigned to the formation of PbI_2 domains. The SEM image of the film prepared at 70 °C exhibits cracks while the film prepared from a substrate heated at 90 °C exhibits a full and homogeneous coverage of the surface. As it has previously been pointed out, the HC temperature has a profound impact on the structure and crystallinity of the 2D RP perovskite films which therefore determines the performance of the optoelectronic devices.²⁶ We have selected a HC temperature of 90 °C for our experiments to maximize the percentage of low dimensional 2D RP perovskites in the films and maintaining a high crystallinity.

The solvent used in the deposition of the films is likely the most critical parameter to control the structure, orientation and crystallinity of the 2D RP perovskites. Figure 1 shows the absorption spectra (A) and XRD patterns (B) for the $\text{PEA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ films prepared from different DMF:DMSO solutions (10:0, 9:1, 7:3 and 5:5). The absorption spectra exhibit the typical exciton bands associated to the 2D RP perovskites with $n = 1$ (525 nm), $n = 2$ (570 nm), $n = 3$ (610 nm), $n = 4$ (642 nm) and an absorption onset around 760 nm related to the materials with high n values including the 3D MAPbI_3 perovskite ($n = \infty$).²⁸ The presence of all these absorption bands clearly indicates that the films contain a distribution of 2D RP perovskites with different n values due the thermodynamic mixing during the film casting.²⁹ However, the exact percentage of each material with different n value is not achievable from the absorption measurements since the absorption coefficients are unknown. Moreover, the absorption capacity of the low dimensional 2D RP perovskites ($n < 5$) is larger compared to that of the materials with high n values, which generates a disproportionate absorption signal with respect to their actual concentration. Nevertheless, the relative intensity of the different peaks can be utilized to gain an insight into changes in the distribution of the 2D RP perovskites. The analysis of the absorption spectra reveals tha the absorption onset at 760 nm is very prominent at lower DMF contents while the absorption signal at 610 nm is comparatively more intense at higher DMF percentages. Thus, the DMF solvent induces a change in the distribution of 2D RP perovskite to low n values, and especially to the stoichiometric

PEA₂MA₂Pb₃I₁₀ structure ($n = 3$), while the DMSO solvent produces the opposite effect, higher percentages of perovskite with high n values. This agrees with the higher power conversion efficiencies (PCEs) obtained in 2D RP perovskite devices prepared from solutions containing certain percentages of DMSO compared with those prepared with only DMF due to the optimal properties for photovoltaics of the 2D RP perovskites with higher n values. However, the enhanced PCE value when adding DMSO is at expenses to the lower stability of the devices compared to those containing 2D RP perovskites with lower n values (lower PCE).²⁷

Figure 1. Absorption spectra (A) and X-ray diffraction patterns (B and C) of films of PEA₂MA₂Pb₃I₁₀ prepared from different solvents: DMF (black line) and DMF:DMSO ratio of 9:1 (blue line), 7:3 (red line) and 5:5 (orange line).

Regarding the XRD patterns of the different films, there is a clear reduction in the number of reflection peaks when decreasing the content of DMSO (see Figure 1B and S4A). At high DMSO content, the Bragg reflections below 12.00° are assigned to the (00l) planes. In particular, the peaks at 3.90°, 7.80°, and 11.70° are assigned to the (001), (002) and (003) planes of the $n = 2$ material while peaks at 5.37° and 10.77° correspond to the (001) and (002) planes of the $n = 1$ material.^{7,30} Moreover, the peak at 31.70° also indicates the presence of the 3D MAPbI₃ perovskite which agrees well with that observed in the absorption measurements.³¹ On the other hand, the most intense peaks in all DMF:DMSO ratio (see Figure 1B) are attributed to crystallographic planes horizontally oriented to the substrate corresponding to a combination of the 2D RP perovskites with different n values. The presence of multiple reflections in the samples with higher DMSO content indicates a random orientation of the RP phases while the existence of only two Bragg peaks in the films deposited with DMF proves the

preferential orientation of the 2D RP phases with the PEA layers perpendicular to the substrate which has been shown to be beneficial to improve the charge transport through the film.⁹ Additionally, a closer view of the region of the XRD patterns covering the more intense Bragg peaks (see Figure 2C) shows a different 2θ position for those peaks depending on the used solvent. The three films containing DMSO present reflection peaks at 14.08° and 28.38° associated to the (110) and (220) planes of the 3D MAPbI₃ perovskite (see Figure S4B) while the films prepared from DMF display Bragg peaks at 14.15° and 28.56° assigned to the same reflection peaks but with their position altered by the higher concentration of low dimensional 2D RP perovskites in this film. We have selected DMF as the precursor solvent to achieve preferentially oriented films with larger contents of low dimensional perovskites, in particular the PEA₂MA₂Pb₃I₁₀ structure ($n = 3$).

The concentration of the precursors (PEAI, MAI and PbI₂) in the initial solution is the third factor that may affect the structure and orientation of the 2D RP perovskite films. Although it is not frequently studied in the bibliography, it has been noted that the fabrication of thick films is one the major challenges in the field of 2D layered perovskite devices, given its reduced absorption in the red side of the visible spectrum.³² Figure S5A illustrates the good linear relationship between the absorption intensity of the films and the concentration of precursors, [PbI₂] = 0.4, 0.6, 0.8 and 1.2 M, certainly indicating a gradual increase of the thickness of the film with no changes in the relative ratio of the different n structures. The XRD patterns (Figure S5B) exhibit no changes in the position, intensity and width of the Bragg reflections and no new signals are detected. Thus, the decrease of the concentration of precursors does not modify the orientation, crystallinity or distribution of the phases with different n values in our 2D RP perovskite based on the PEA and MA cations. We have selected an intermediate concentration, [PbI₂] = 0.6 M, since the absorption signal is optimal for photovoltaic devices.

Once the experimental conditions are optimized to obtain highly crystalline and preferentially oriented 2D RP perovskite films and with higher content of low dimensional phases, in particular the PEA₂MA₂Pb₃I₁₀ structure ($n = 3$), we have investigated the sequential addition of the Gua cation to the films. The concentration of the PEA cation is maintained constant in the precursor solution

varying only the relative concentration of the MA and Gua cations. Figure 2A displays the normalized absorption spectra at 655 nm of the $\text{PEA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite films upon increasing the Gua content from 5% to 30%. Although the particular concentration of each 2D RP perovskite with different n value cannot be determined, the changes in the relative intensity of the absorption signals allow identifying modifications of the distribution of the 2D RP phases. Thus, the two more relevant features when adding the Gua cation are the reduced absorption signal at the long wavelength region (650-775 nm) and the rise of the signals at 570 nm ($n = 2$), 610 nm ($n = 3$) and 642 nm ($n = 4$). The increase of the absorption signals related to the low dimensional perovskites ($n = 2, 3$ and 4) is progressive up to 15-20% of Gua, then remains constant in 20-25% and finally rises again at 30%, but only in the peak related to the $n = 2$ material. These results are in opposition to those observed in the 3D MAPbI_3 perovskite where the addition of the Gua cation yielded no significant changes in the absorption band edge up to a value of 25% Gua.²³ Our experimental observations reveal a modification of the distribution of the n values in the 2D RP perovskites when replacing the MA by the Gua cation. Thus, the 2D RP perovskites with high n values are not preferentially formed at high Gua content while the growth of low dimensional perovskites ($n = 2, 3$ and 4) is favored. In case of the film with 30% Gua content, the increase of the absorption signal at 570 nm ($n = 2$) is significant with respect to the other percentages which indicates that an enrichment in the $n = 2$ member is taking place. Figure 2B exhibits the absorption spectra of the same $\text{PEA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite films at higher Gua content, from 40% to 90%. The extra addition of the Gua cation to the film produces a sequential disappearance of the absorption peaks related to the $n = 3$ - and 4 -members together with an increase of the signal associated to the $n = 2$ -member, remaining only this RP phase at 90% Gua content. The substitution of the MA cation for the Gua cation on the 2D RP layered perovskites promotes the formation of low dimensional RP perovskites, similarly to the control of the crystallization process together with the addition of additives recently published as a strategy to obtain pure phases of the 2D RP perovskites.³³⁻³⁵ In our approach, the higher Gua content is utilized in the initial stoichiometry, the lower n value of the RP phases is obtained, producing a narrowing of the distribution to the low n values.

Figure 2. Normalized absorption spectra at 655 nm (A) and absorption spectra (B) of the $\text{PEA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite films upon addition of different contents of Gua: from 0 to 30% (A) and from 40 to 90% (B).

The remarkable influence of the Gua cation in the population of the n -members is expected to be related to the incorporation of the Gua cation into the structure of the 2D RP perovskite and, therefore, X-ray diffraction measurements are performed to analyze the crystalline structure. Figure 3A shows the XRD patterns of the $\text{PEA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ structure upon increasing the Gua content from 5% to 90%. The addition of Gua does not produce the appearance of new reflection peaks (see also Figure S6) up to a value of 30% Gua content which indicates that no new crystallographic phases or loss of a preferential orientation takes place below this percentage of Gua. At 40-50% Gua content, only a small reflection peak at 5.36° is observed which is assigned to the PEA_2PbI_4 2D perovskite. At higher Gua content (60-90%), significant Bragg peaks at 4.20° and 8.45° are visible which correspond to the (00l) planes of low dimensional ($n < 5$) 2D RP perovskites, pointing out a partial loss of preferential orientation of the perovskite crystals. Figure 3B displays a magnification of the more intense Bragg reflections where the effect of the Gua cation can be clearly detected. The main two reflection peaks at 14.15° and 28.56° in the films without Gua correspond to the (110) and (220) planes of the 2D RP perovskites. The simulated XRD pattern of the $\text{PEA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite predicts that the (110) and (220) reflections should appear at 14.45° and 29.14° but the broad distribution of 2D RP phases in the film with different n values shifts the position of these peaks to lower angles and produces a broadening of the peaks.⁷ The increase of the Gua content up to 20% produces a gradual shift of the peaks to lower angles (from 14.15° to 14.06° and

from 28.56° to 28.43°) but without altering the width of the reflection peaks. We attribute this behavior due to the sequential incorporation of the Gua cation into the “perovskite slabs” by direct substitution of the MA cation generating the mixed cation $\text{PEA}_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{Gua}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite. Thus, the larger ionic radius of the Gua cation compared to that of the MA cation yields a regular expansion of the unit cell of the 2D RP perovskites.^{23,25} At 25% of Gua, the XRD pattern shows two overlapped peaks for both (110) and (220) planes that evolves in the disappearance of the high-angle peaks (14.05° and 28.45°) at 30% of Gua while the low-angle peaks (13.97° and 28.15°) remains in the XRD pattern. Interestingly, the two reflection peaks at 30% of Gua are narrower compared to those measured at percentages of Gua below 25%. The extra addition of Gua reveals a gradual shift of the two main Bragg reflections to lower angles (13.85° and 27.95° at 90% Gua content) but maintaining the same reduced width of the peaks. We attribute the further displacement of the peaks to the continuous incorporation of Gua instead of the MA cation in the 2D RP phase as it was described at percentages below 25% of Gua. However, the clear change in the width of the peaks when going from 25% to 30% Gua content indicates a sudden change in the arrangement of the mixed cation $\text{PEA}_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{Gua}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskites. The width of the reflection peaks depends on the crystallite size, micro-strain of the structures and, in this case, the distribution of n -members of the 2D RP perovskites.²³ Since the crystallite size in the films is not modified (see SEM measurements below) and the micro-strain should increase with the incorporation of the larger Gua cation, the decrease of the width of the reflection peaks at percentages of Gua higher than 30% must be related to a severe restriction in the distribution of n -members of the 2D RP perovskites, constraining the population mainly to the $n = 2$ -, 3- and 4-members. The absorption measurements strongly support this conclusion since a significant decrease of the signal from the materials with high n values together with a rise of the absorption from the low dimensional RP perovskites is observed above 30% Gua content. Thus, the Gua cation is gradually incorporated into the “perovskite slabs” of the $\text{PEA}_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{Gua}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite in the whole Gua content range, causing a reduction of the 2D RP phases with high n values and a rise of the population of low dimensional members ($n < 5$) from the initial addition of Gua but

with a significant change at 30% Gua content where essentially appear only the $n = 2$ -, 3- and 4-members.

Figure 3. XRD patterns of the $\text{PEA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite films upon addition of different contents of Gua: 0%, 5%, 10%, 15%, 20%, 25%, 30%, 40%, 50%, 60%, 70%, 80% and 90%.

To complete the investigation of the Gua incorporation into the 2D RP perovskites, we have also added the Gua cation in films prepared from $\text{PEA}_2\text{MAPb}_2\text{I}_7$ ($n = 2$) and $\text{PEA}_2\text{MA}_3\text{Pb}_4\text{I}_{13}$ ($n = 4$) stoichiometries. Figure S7 displays the absorption and XRD patterns for both films with a Gua content from 5% to 40%. The absorption spectrum of the $\text{PEA}_2\text{MAPb}_2\text{I}_7$ film (Figure S7A) exhibits a very intense absorption signal associated to the $n = 2$ -member, a moderate signal at 517 nm related to $n = 1$ -member and weak peaks related to the members with higher n values. Regarding the $\text{PEA}_2\text{MA}_3\text{Pb}_4\text{I}_{13}$ film (Figure S7C), the absorption signals for the low dimensional phases ($n < 5$) are comparable and an intense absorption onset at 760 nm related to the phases with high n values is present. The addition of the Gua cation entails small changes in the $\text{PEA}_2\text{MAPb}_2\text{I}_7$ film since the low dimensional phases already prevails, however, in the $\text{PEA}_2\text{MA}_3\text{Pb}_4\text{I}_{13}$ film, it causes the rise of the $n = 2$ -, 3- and 4-members at expenses of the phases with high n values or with $n = 1$. On the other hand, the XRD pattern of the $\text{PEA}_2\text{MAPb}_2\text{I}_7$ film (Figure S7B) shows peaks around 14.16° and 28.58° related to the reflections of the (110) and (220) planes of the 2D RP perovskites and also Bragg peaks at 14.25° , 28.78° and 28.92° associated to the PEA_2PbI_4 perovskite ($n = 1$), as expected from the absorption measurements. In the $\text{PEA}_2\text{MA}_3\text{Pb}_4\text{I}_{13}$ film (Figure S7D), the peaks appear at 14.06° and 28.43° which are in good agreement with those observed for the 3D MAPbI_3 perovskite. In both cases, the increase in the Gua content shifts the

peaks to lower angles with a considerable reduction in the width of the peaks at 15% and 30% Gua content in the $\text{PEA}_2\text{MAPb}_2\text{I}_7$ and $\text{PEA}_2\text{MA}_3\text{Pb}_4\text{I}_{13}$ films, respectively. It is worth noting that the peaks related to the $n = 1$ phase in the $\text{PEA}_2\text{MAPb}_2\text{I}_7$ film do not shift because the Gua cation is not incorporated into this structure. The results observed in the $\text{PEA}_2\text{MAPb}_2\text{I}_7$ and $\text{PEA}_2\text{MA}_3\text{Pb}_4\text{I}_{13}$ films are consistent with those obtained in the $\text{PEA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ film, which demonstrates that the Gua cation incorporates into the structure of the 2D RP perovskites producing a narrowing in the distribution of n -members to the low n values.

In addition to the films, powders of the mixed cation $\text{PEA}_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{Gua}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite have also been synthesized by using a mechanochemical process: ball milling. Figure S8 displays the XRD patterns for the perovskite powders with Gua content of 0%, 5%, 15%, 20% and 25% together with the simulated XRD of the 2D RP $\text{PEA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite. The XRD peaks in all samples are relatively broad which reveals the low crystallinity of the powders. Unlike in the highly oriented films, the powders present several intense XRD peaks in the whole 2θ range. Moreover, the position and number of peaks match well with those exhibited in the simulated XRD of the $\text{PEA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite which ensure that the lattice structure of the $\text{PEA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite is maintained upon addition of the Gua cation.

The incorporation of the Gua cation into the structure of the $\text{PEA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite can be also studied by using infrared spectroscopy. The 3D MAPbI_3 and $\text{MA}_{0.90}\text{Gua}_{0.10}\text{PbI}_3$ perovskites and the 2D layered Gua_2PbI_4 phase were synthesized as previously reported^{23,36} and used as references. Figure S9 shows the infrared spectra of the different perovskite films showing the more significant peaks in the $3500\text{-}2900\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region. In the 3D mixed cation $\text{MA}_{0.90}\text{Gua}_{0.10}\text{PbI}_3$ perovskite, where the Gua cation has been proven to be inserted in the octahedral voids, the characteristic vibrations of the Gua cations appears at 3460 cm^{-1} and 3346 cm^{-1} (brown line in Figure S9) corresponding to the asymmetric and symmetric N-H stretching vibrations, respectively.³⁷ The position of these vibrational modes is strongly influenced by the chemical environment as, for example, the counter ion compensating the electrostatic charge or the relative position inside a crystalline structure.^{37,38} Thus, in the 2D layered Gua_2PbI_4 perovskite, the position of the Gua vibrations are shifted to lower frequencies

(3420 cm^{-1} and 3328 cm^{-1}) since the Gua cations are not situated in octahedral voids but in between corrugated layers of $[\text{PbI}_6]^{4-}$ octahedra similarly to the position of the PEA cations in the 2D RP perovskites. Regarding the mixed cation $\text{PEA}_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{Gua}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite, the three films containing 10%, 20% or 40% Gua display vibrational modes at the same frequencies which match with those observed in the 3D mixed cation $\text{MA}_{0.90}\text{Gua}_{0.10}\text{PbI}_3$ perovskite. Moreover, the vibrational peaks in the 3150-2900 cm^{-1} region are assigned to the asymmetric and symmetric stretching modes of the N-H and C-H bonds in the MA cations which are shifted to higher frequencies upon addition of Gua cation due to the distortion in the network created by the Gua cations.³⁹ The previous results prove the insertion of the Gua cation into the octahedral voids of the $\text{PEA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite discarding the hypothetical substitution of the PEA cation by the Gua cation.

The importance of the orientation of the 2D RP phases in the films is notable in several optoelectronic applications since a vertical arrangement of the perovskite slabs will enable an efficient charge transport in this direction.⁹ Thus, we have performed Grazing-Incidence Wide-Angle X-ray Scattering (GIWAXS) measurements of the $\text{PEA}_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{Gua}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskites to assess the influence of the Gua cation on the orientation of the crystalline phases. The analysis of the GIWAXS patterns in Figure 4 and S10 reveals the absence of Debye-Scherrer rings in the films with Gua content below 60% which precludes a randomly oriented structure in the polycrystalline films. Indeed, the GIWAXS patterns of the films with and without Gua display intense (110) and (220) reflections at an azimuthal angles $\chi = 0^\circ$ demonstrating the vertical orientation of the perovskite slabs with respect to the substrate. The identical GIWAXS patterns among the different films clearly indicates that the insertion of Gua does not alter the preferential orientation of the perovskites slabs which are positioned perpendicular to the substrate. In the films with a Gua content above 60%, it is visible the appearance of diffraction rings that are associated to a more disordered structure which fits well with the previously studied XDR patterns.

Figure 4. 2D GIWAXS patterns of $\text{PEA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ (A), and three mixed cation $\text{PEA}_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{Gua}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ with 5% (B), 15% (C) and 25% (D) Gua perovskite films.

In the 3D hybrid perovskites, the partial incorporation of the Gua cation into the octahedral voids of the $[\text{PbI}_6]^{4-}$ network is limited to a 25% since an extra addition of Gua originates profound distortions of the structure making it not stable.²³ However, our XRD measurements have revealed that a higher percentage of Gua can be inserted into the $\text{PEA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite with a preferential incorporation of the Gua cation into the phases with low n value. To investigate the degree of distortions caused by the Gua cation, theoretical calculations have been performed in the mixed cation $\text{PEA}_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{Gua}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskites containing a Gua content of 25% and 50%. These two structures have been built by direct replacement of the corresponding content of MA by Gua in the $\text{PEA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite and then a global optimization of the geometry has been performed including the unit cell. Figure S11 displays the optimized structure for the 2D RP $\text{PEA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite and those including a 25% and 50% Gua content. The modeled structures reflect the low distortions in the $[\text{PbI}_6]^{4-}$ network upon addition of the Gua cation even at contents as high as 50%

demonstrating the high stability of the mixed cation 2D RP perovskites. Figure 5 shows the Pb-I distances and the Pb-I-Pb angles in an octahedral void for each mixed cation $\text{PEA}_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{Gua}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite. The average value of the Pb-I distances of the external side of the cavity in contact with the PEA cations is $3.156 \pm 0.023 \text{ \AA}$ in the $\text{PEA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ phase, while it turns out to be $3.199 \pm 0.024 \text{ \AA}$ and $3.272 \pm 0.196 \text{ \AA}$ with 25 % and 50% Gua content, respectively. The previous values demonstrate the gradual expansion of the cell upon increasing the Gua content but only up to moderate values suitable for the Pb-I bond. The Pb-I-Pb angles also reflect the small distortions in the structure with an average value of $155.9^\circ \pm 0.4^\circ$ in the phase without Gua and with values of $151.3^\circ \pm 2.8^\circ$ and $156.7^\circ \pm 1.5^\circ$ in the samples with 25% and 50% Gua, respectively. Regarding the internal side of the octahedral cavity in contact with the adjacent cavity in the $n = 3$ phase, both Pb-I distances and Pb-I-Pb angles are still similar within the three materials although slightly more distorted with respect to those found in the external side. Thus, the Pb-I distances are $3.171 \pm 0.029 \text{ \AA}$, $3.244 \pm 0.034 \text{ \AA}$ and $3.304 \pm 0.201 \text{ \AA}$ and the Pb-I-Pb angles are $152.0^\circ \pm 4.3^\circ$, $148.7^\circ \pm 7.7^\circ$ and $151.9^\circ \pm 2.3^\circ$ in the films without and with 25% and 50% Gua content, respectively. These results corroborate the feasible formation of mixed cation $\text{PEA}_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{Gua}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskites with Gua contents higher than 25% in opposition to the situation in the 3D MAPbI_3 perovskite. Therefore, the low dimensional $\text{PEA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite is capable of releasing the distortions caused by the Gua cations throughout the entire inorganic network without provoking the breaking of the Pb-I bonds. We can conclude that the actual range of the Goldschmidt tolerance factor ($0.8 < t < 1.0$) for feasible 3D phases is not applicable to the 2D RP $\text{PEA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite which paves the way to the insertion of other types of A cations in the layered RP perovskites. The high flexibility of the low dimensional $\text{PEA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite to accommodate the large Gua cation into its structure is related to the preferential incorporation of Gua to the phases with low n values. The enthalpy of reaction (ΔH) of the chemical process involving the incorporation of 25% Gua content to the 3D MAPbI_3 perovskite ($n = \infty$) or to the 2D RP $\text{PEA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite ($n = 3$) has been theoretically calculated according to reaction (1):

The calculated ΔH value of reaction (1) is -154.025 eV which proves that the incorporation of the Gua cation to the low dimensional perovskite ($n = 3$) is energetically more favorable with respect to the insertion in the 3D material. This result agrees with the experimental evidence observed in the XRD and absorption experiments. In addition to this, the ΔH value for the insertion of additional Gua into the $PEA_2(MA_{0.75}Gua_{0.25})_2Pb_3I_{10}$ perovskite to form the $PEA_2(MA_{0.50}Gua_{0.50})_2Pb_3I_{10}$ perovskite has been calculated following reaction (2):

A value of -1.584 eV has been obtained for the ΔH of reaction (2), demonstrating that the incorporation of up to 50% Gua in the $PEA_2MA_2Pb_3I_{10}$ perovskite is energetically allowable although with a low energy driving force. This low value might lead to degradation issues in the 2D RP perovskite with high Gua content as it occurs in the 3D $MAPbI_3$ perovskite.

Figure 5. Octahedral perovskite cavity of the 2D RP $\text{PEA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ (left), $\text{PEA}_2(\text{MA}_{0.75}\text{Gua}_{0.25})_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ (middle) and $\text{PEA}_2(\text{MA}_{0.50}\text{Gua}_{0.50})_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ (right) showing the corresponding organic cation MA (left) or Gua (middle and right) and the Pb-I distances (upper panel) and Pb-I-Pb angles (lower panel).

The 2D RP perovskite films typically exhibit pinholes or cracks and therefore, many efforts have been done to prepare homogeneous films that might be implemented in optoelectronic devices.^{40,41} The morphology of the $\text{PEA}_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{Gua}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite films has been assessed by using Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM). Figure 6 and S12 display the SEM images of the $\text{PEA}_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{Gua}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite films. The $\text{PEA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ film (panel A in Figure 6) is reasonably homogeneous with full coverage of the surface since no pinholes are observed. A densely packed grain structure can be observed with grain sizes in the range of 200-400 nm and with smooth grain boundaries. However, the film is not completely flat and some small protuberances can be noticed which might be detrimental for charge transport. Regarding the films with Gua, the analysis of the SEM images reveals that the incorporation of Gua does not modify considerably the morphology of the films, at least up to a value of 50% Gua content. The packed grain structure is conserved with similar grain sizes although a higher concentration of protuberances is visible. At high Gua content (> 60%), the films present well-defined voids with straight edges and elongated particles. An energy dispersive X-ray (EDX) analysis has also performed to quantify the elemental

composition of the films. Figures S13-S15 displays the EDX profile analysis for three mixed cation perovskites with Gua content of 0%, 30% and 80%. Table S4 shows the atomic percentage of C, Pb and I where the Pb/I ratio is close to the theoretical one (0.3) in all films and the relative percentages are practically the same independent of the Gua content. Moreover, the EDX mapping proves a homogeneous distribution of the three atoms through the entire surface.

Figure 6. Top-surface SEM images of $\text{PEA}_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{Gua}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite films with different Gua contents: 0% (A), 20% (B), 40% (C) and 90% (D). Scale bar, 2 μm .

The modification of the structure of the $\text{PEA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite by the incorporation of the Gua cation entails significant changes in the optoelectronic properties of these materials. Figure 7A illustrates the photoluminescence (PL) spectra for the $\text{PEA}_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{Gua}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite films in a Gua range from 0% to 60% after excitation at 400 nm where all n materials absorb light. In the film without the Gua cation, the typical PL peak at 759 nm is detected together with weaker PL signals at 572 nm, 622 nm and 662 nm which are associated to the PL emission of the $n = 2$ -, 3- and 4-members, respectively. The intense PL signal at 759 nm in the $\text{PEA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ film is blue-shifted compared to the PL peak of the 3D MAPbI_3 perovskite appearing at 780 nm, as it also occurred with the absorption band edge due the confinement effect.⁴² The addition of Gua to the 2D RP phases produces a gradual increase of the PL peak associated to the material with higher n value up to about 50% Gua content. Figure 7B displays the normalized PL peaks of the $\text{PEA}_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{Gua}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite films where a systematic blue shift of the maximum of the peak is observed when increasing the Gua content. Both effects, growth and shift to higher energies of the PL signal are accounted for due to the larger quantum confinement effect in the materials with higher Gua content.⁴³ This is a conclusive evidence of the sequential narrowing of the distribution of n -members towards those with low n values upon

increasing the Gua content which is in good agreement with the results observed in the absorption experiments. Thus, the $\text{PEA}_2(\text{MA}_{0.50}\text{Gua}_{0.50})_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite film (50% Gua) exhibits a notable 25 times increase of the PL signal while maintaining the PL signal around 725-750 nm and with a preferential orientation of the perovskite structure. In addition, more significant PL changes are observed at percentages of Gua higher than 60%. Figure 7C shows the normalized PL spectra for $\text{PEA}_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{Gua}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite films with Gua content $\geq 70\%$ where the PL peaks centered at 688 nm, 662 nm, 622 nm and 572 nm correspond to the PL signal linked to the $n = 5$ -, 4-, 3- and 2-members, respectively. Thus, it is possible to control the origin of the PL signal coming from a particular n -member ($n = 2, 3, 4, \text{ or } 5$) by selecting a specific percentage of Gua in the 2D RP perovskite. The subtle modification in the distribution of n -members caused at the high percentages of the Gua cation produces substantial changes in the position of the PL peaks. The fine tuning of the PL position might have important applications in certain optoelectronic devices, as for example in light-emitting diodes.

Figure 7. (A) PL spectra of $\text{PEA}_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{Gua}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite films with Gua content from 0% to 60%. (B) Normalized PL spectra of the same perovskite films as in (A). (C) PL spectra of $\text{PEA}_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{Gua}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite films with Gua content from 70% to 90%.

Figure S16 depicts the time-resolved PL decay of different $\text{PEA}_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{Gua}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite films obtained at low fluence ($1 \mu\text{J}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$) where only monomolecular recombination should be effective. A triexponential fit of the data has been performed (Table S5), resulting in longer carrier lifetimes when increased the Gua content up to a 50%. However, at 60% and 80% Gua content, the carrier lifetimes decrease to values lower than those for the $\text{PEA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite revealing the more excitonic character of the excited state in those

films since mainly include low n -members ($n = 2$). The longer decays of the PL signal until 50% Gua content correlates well with the increasing PL signals measured in the steady-state measurements. Since the monomolecular recombination in 3D and 2D perovskites is dominated by the non-radiative charge-carrier trapping at impurities, we ascribe the longer PL decays in the $\text{PEA}_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{Gua}_x)_2\text{Pb}_{310}$ perovskite films ($0 < x < 0.50$) to a lower concentration of traps in those films containing mainly the $n = 3, 4$ and 5 members.⁴²

To complete the photophysical analysis of the mixed cation $\text{PEA}_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{Gua}_x)_2\text{Pb}_{310}$ perovskites, femto- to picosecond transient absorption spectroscopy was performed to get insight into the ultrafast deactivation mechanisms of these materials. Figure 8 and S17 display the transient absorption spectra upon excitation at $\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 400$ nm where all n -members of the 2D RP perovskite absorb light. The spectra exhibit mainly negative signals due to photobleaching, with maxima at 570 nm, 612 nm, 650 nm and 710 nm ascribed to the $n = 2$ -, 3 -, 4 - and ∞ -members, respectively. However, the relative intensity of the photobleaching signals changes in the different films. Thus, the negative signal associated to the 2D RP perovskites with large n values (> 700 nm) is only visible in the perovskite films with 0% and 10% Gua content which indicates that those high n -members are not formed at high Gua content. In addition, the increasing amount of Gua in the perovskite structure causes the rise of the transient signals related to the low n -members at the expense of the other members. For example, the photobleaching signal at 570 nm ($n = 2$) is by far the major one in the sample with 70% Gua content with a moderate signal at 612 nm ($n = 3$) and an almost negligible signal at 650 nm ($n = 4$). The previous results are in good agreement with those obtained in the steady-state absorption measurements proving that by selecting the percentage of Gua in the mixed cation 2D RP perovskite, it is possible to control the relative concentration of the n -members. The deactivation mechanisms after photoexcitation can be monitored by analyzing the evolution of the photobleaching peaks at the different delay times. Interestingly, the transient signals in the short time scale of the $\text{PEA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_{310}$ perovskite film display a rapid decay of the $n = 2$ - and 3 -members concomitant with a rise in the signals associated to the $n = 5$ and higher n -members. To analyze quantitatively this behavior, Figure 8D exhibits the transient decays for the significant wavelengths related to each photobleaching peak in the

PEA₂MA₂Pb₃I₁₀ perovskite film. The global fit of the data reveals time constant of $\tau_1 = 0.45$ ps, $\tau_2 = 5$ ps and $\tau_3 = 214$ ps. The fastest time constant presents negative amplitude at the peaks related to the $n = 2, 3$ and 4 members while it shows positive amplitude for the signals assigned to the $n = 5$ and higher n -members which indicates a transfer of population from the low to the high n -members. The funneling of the photogenerated excitons in the low dimensional perovskites to those with higher n values *via* an energy transfer process has recently been reported as the mechanism responsible for the ultrafast deactivation of the PEA₂MA₂Pb₃I₁₀ perovskite.²⁹ Regarding the other two time constants, a negative amplitude is derived for all photobleaching peaks with carrier recombination as the most likely deactivation mechanism.²⁹ The transient kinetics observed in all mixed cation PEA₂(MA_{1-x}Gua_x)₂Pb₃I₁₀ perovskite films are similar to those found in the reference film. Thus, the decay of the photobleaching peaks assigned to the n -members with low n values ($n = 2$ and 3) occurs simultaneously to the rise of the of the peaks related to the high n -members which proves that the energy transfer process is also an active deactivation mechanism in the 2D RP PEA₂(MA_{1-x}Gua_x)₂Pb₃I₁₀ perovskites.

Figure 8. Transient absorption spectra at different delay times (A, B and C) and time decays at $\lambda_{\text{probe}} = 570 \text{ nm}$, 612 nm , 650 nm and 710 nm (D, E and F) of mixed cation $\text{PEA}_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{Gua}_x)_2\text{Pb}_{310}$ perovskite films with 0% (A and D), 30% (B and E) and 70% (C and F) Gua content. $\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 400 \text{ nm}$.

The enhanced stability of the 3D mixed cation $\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{Gua}_x\text{PbI}_3$ perovskites has previously been proven due to the increase in the number of hydrogen bonds by the Gua cation that stabilizes the network of corner-sharing $[\text{PbI}_6]^{4-}$ octahedra.²³ Thus, the incorporation of the Gua cation in the $\text{PEA}_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{Gua}_x)_2\text{Pb}_{310}$ perovskites is expected to extend the stability of these 2D RP perovskites. Figure

S18 shows photographs of mixed cation $\text{PEA}_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{Gua}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite films with 0%, 5%, 10%, 15%, 20%, 25%, 40% and 60% Gua content taken at different days after their preparation and conserved in dark at fixed relative humidity (RH) and temperature conditions ($\sim 50\%$ RH and 25°C) without encapsulation. Thus, the films without Gua and with high Gua content (40% and 60%) are completely degraded after 45 days while the films with a Gua content between 5% and 25% maintain their dark color proving the higher stability of the films with moderate concentration of Gua. Figure S19 shows the XRD patterns of some of the previous $\text{PEA}_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{Gua}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite films (0%, 10%, 20%, 40% and 60% Gua content) at four different days. The degradation of the 2D RP perovskites is tracked by the decrease in the intensity of the main reflection peak around 14° and the appearance of a Bragg reflection at 12.6° associated to the PbI_2 which is the principal degradation compound. The evolution of the signals clearly demonstrate that the $\text{PEA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite without Gua is almost completely degraded after 45 days while the structure of the 2D RP phases with 10% and 20% Gua is conserved. Regarding the films with 40% and 60% Gua content, we observe the appearance of new reflection peaks and the decrease of the intensity of the peaks around 14° and 25.8° which indicates the partial degradation of these films.

Figure 9. *J-V* curve of the champion solar cells prepared with the mixed cation $\text{PEA}_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{Gua}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskites with 0% (A), 10% (B), 20% (C) and 40% (D) Gua content.

To prove the potential incorporation of these materials in photovoltaics, we have fabricated solar devices with a n-i-p mesoscopic architecture including the $\text{PEA}_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{Gua}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite films as the active layer. Figure 9 exhibits the *J-V* curves together with the average photovoltaic parameters (10 devices) obtained from cells containing Gua percentages of 0%, 10%, 20% or 40%. The short-circuit current density (J_{sc}) barely changes for Gua content up to 20% ($J_{sc} = 7.48 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$), but rapidly decreases in the device with 40% Gua content ($J_{sc} = 4.68 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$). The reduction of the absorption signal related to the high *n*-members observed in the films with high Gua content accounts for the lower J_{sc} found in the device with 40% Gua content. Besides, the average open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}) slightly increases with the sequential addition of Gua, from 0.86 V for $x = 0$ to 0.89 V for $x = 0.40$, which might be linked to a shift of the conduction and valence bands as it occurred in the 3D mixed cation $\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{Gua}_x\text{PbI}_3$ perovskites.²³ Regarding the fill factor (FF), we do not observe changes with

increasing percentage of Gua, obtaining an average value over 0.42. Thus, the PCE values of the solar devices remain practically the same for the samples with $x = 0$ (2.69%), $x = 0.10$ (2.79%) and $x = 0.20$ (2.70%) Gua content, but decreases to a PCE = 1.86% in the device with $x = 0.40$ due to the lower J_{sc} value. This value of PCE is comparable with that previously reported in solar cells fabricated with the 2D RP $PEA_2MA_2Pb_3I_{10}$ perovskite with the same architecture and hole and electron transporting layers.⁷

Figure 10. Stability test of solar cells prepared with the mixed cation $PEA_2(MA_{1-x}Gua_x)_2Pb_3I_{10}$ perovskites with 0%, 10%, 20% and 40% Gua content conserved in dark under constant fixed relative humidity (RH) and temperature conditions (~50% RH and 25 °C) without encapsulation.

The stability of the 2D RP mixed cation perovskites has also been studied within a solar device.^{4,44,45} The unencapsulated devices were stored in dark at stable humidity and temperature (50% RH and 25 °C) for more than 750 hours. Figure 10 reveals a notable reduction of the normalized PCE value to a 40% of the initial one in the device without Gua ($PEA_2MA_2Pb_3I_{10}$) after 750 hours while it drops to 80% of the initial value in the devices with 10% and 20% of Gua. The behavior of the sample with 40% Gua content is more complex, with a sharp decrease of the PCE after 200 hours followed by a stabilization of the PCE to a 60% of the initial one after 750 hours. Thus, the incorporation of Gua to the 2D RP phases slows down the perovskite degradation which proves the importance of the cation-

engineering approach in the extension of the lifetime of the perovskite solar devices.

Conclusions

The Gua cation is incorporated into the octahedral voids of the “perovskite slabs” of 2D RP perovskites in a percentage much higher (up to 90%) than those reported for the 3D perovskites (limit of 25%). This is explained due to the more flexible structure of the 2D RP phases where the distortions/strain caused by the Gua cation is less meaningful. Thus, the Goldschmidt tolerance factor applicable to the 3D perovskites is not valid in the 2D perovskites which open the way to the insertion of a wider variety of *A*-cations.

The insertion of Gua into the mixed cation $\text{PEA}_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{Gua}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite is preferentially produced into the low dimensional ($n < 5$) phases which yields a change in the distribution of the *n*-members. Thus, by selecting the appropriate percentage of Gua, it is possible to control the concentration of *n*-members in the 2D RP perovskite.

The addition of Gua allows to control the optoelectronic properties of the 2D RP perovskite. The intensity of the infrared PL signal around 750 nm can be modulated by varying the Gua content, with a 25 times increase at 50% of Gua. More importantly, the position of the PL signal in the visible region (550-700 nm) can be adjusted to that of the $n = 5, 4, 3$ and 2 by rising the Gua content from 70% to 90%.

Solar cells fabricated with the mixed cation 2D RP perovskite exhibit similar PCE values to those previously reported for the $\text{PEA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite. The stability tests have shown a significant enhancement of the lifetime of the solar cells containing the Gua cation incorporated in the 2D RP perovskite.

Our *A*-cation engineering approach in 2D RP perovskites involves a fine tuning of the distribution of the *n*-members and therefore, of their corresponding optoelectronic properties and more importantly, without affecting the preferential parallel orientation of the 2D RP phases which is optimal for many optoelectronic applications.

Supporting Information

Details about the films and device fabrication. ^1H NMR of the precursor solution, SEM images at different HC temperatures, XRD data of films prepared at different concentration of the precursors, used DMF:DMSO ratio and different initial stoichiometry, XRD data of powders, 2D GIWAXS patterns, theoretical simulated structures, SEM images of the other Gua contents, EDX profile analysis and mapping, time-resolved PL data, femto- to picosecond transient absorption spectroscopy, XRD data of the films at different times.

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